

Growing Inequality:
a Novel Integration of
transformations research

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D2.2 Report on learning from national data sources and guidelines for a harmonised use of data

WP2 Data Harmonisation for Integrated Analysis

Authors:	Majda Seghir, Oksana Nezhyvenko, Sylvie Hamon-Cholet
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WP leader:	CNAM

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Author/s:	<i>Majda Seghir, Oksana Nezhyvenko, & Sylvie Hamon-Cholet</i>
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Summary

In this report, we explore opportunities to enrich and improve European data sources based on national level data collection experiences concerning GI-NI topics, technological change, globalisation, migration, and their respective impacts on the labour market. We analyse the capabilities of several national level data sources. New measurement frames and methodologies to tackle issues covered by the project are reviewed and assessed. Their transferability at the EU-wide level is explored over the course of the whole project.

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Abbreviations

ADMIN3	Hungarian Administrative Linked Employer-Employee Dataset
AMS	Arbeitsmarktservice (Public Employment Service-PES), vacancy register of the Austrian PES
BSD	Balance Sheet Database in Hungary
CEU	Central European University
CIS	Community Innovation Survey
CVTS	Continuing Vocational Training Survey
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
ECS	European Company Survey
EU	European Union
EU-LFS	European Union Labour Force Survey
EU-SILC	European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions
ESEE	Encuesta Sobre Estrategias Empresariales
ESES	European Structure of Earnings Survey
ESS	European Social Survey
EWCS	European Working Conditions Survey
ExIm	Export-Import Database in Hungary
HCS	Hungarian Customs Statistics
HCSO	Hungarian Central Statistical Office
HSES	Hungarian Structure of Earning Survey
IAB	Institut für Arbeitsmarkt (Institute for Employment Research) in Germany
ICT	Information and communication technologies
INE	Instituto Nacional de Estadística (National Statistics Institute) in Spain
ISCO	International Standard Classification of Occupations
MCVL	Muestra Continua de Vidas Laborales (Continuous Working Life Survey) in Spain
MSUS	Material and Service Use Survey in Hungary
NACE	Nomenclature statistique des Activités économiques dans la Communauté Européenne (Statistical classification of economic activities) in the EU

NUTS	Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
OSA	Organisatie voor Strategisch Arbeidsmarktonderzoek (Organisation for Strategic Labor Market Research) in the Netherlands
PES	Public Employment Service
PRODCOM	Production Communautaire Survey in Hungary
R&D	Research and development
SES	Structure of Earnings Survey
SOC	Standard Occupational Classification
SOEP	German Socio-Economic Panel
WB	World Bank
WIOD	World Input-Output Database
ZEW	Leibniz Centre for European Economic Research in Germany

1. Introduction

This report provides a strong justification for enriching European-level datasets by integrating data from national sources in order to enhance labour market research. This is especially important given the current limitations of EU-wide data in adequately addressing the key topics of the GI-NI project, which include technological change, globalisation, migration, and their respective impacts on the labour market.

Existing EU data sources often fall short in providing the precision, depth and coverage needed to fully understand these complex issues. By incorporating national data configurations, the report aims to demonstrate how this can bridge data gaps and enhance the robustness of labour market analysis across Europe. Within the GI-NI project, several national datasets were successfully used for labour market analysis in Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Germany, Hungary, the Netherlands, and Spain. In this report, we provide examples of the use of national databases in relevant analysis, demonstrating how national data sources can complement and enrich European data in a context of labour market research, with a specific focus on technological change, globalisation, and migration. We explore the challenges of linking employee and employer datasets and the potential solutions that national data frameworks offer for improving the breadth and depth of EU-level data. The report also discusses potential solutions to harmonise these diverse data sources, emphasizing the value of national frameworks through capturing, for every country, labour market dynamics that European-level datasets might overlook.

2. Importance of National Data Configurations

National data¹ configurations can provide detailed insights into the labour markets of individual countries and fill gaps that currently exist in European-level data sources. Below we underscore the advantages of leveraging national datasets. Some countries adopt methods of linking employee-employer framework, by integrating data from both sides of the labour equation, employers and employees. These approaches play a crucial role in labour market analysis and provide us a comprehensive view of labour market dynamics, allowing for a better understanding of the interactions between employer practices and employee outcomes, such as wage determination, job quality, and productivity. We also provide several cases of how national datasets are linked with EU-level datasets. Below we focus on three key assessments: of technological change, globalisation, and migration.

National datasets offer a more accurate and precise view of how technological change, globalisation, and migration influence national labour markets. The report examines specific measures derived from national data used in the GI-NI project that provide a more nuanced understanding of these dynamics. We also provide various measures and indicators used in national reports to illustrate how each factor interacts with labour markets at the national level.

2.1. Technological change and labour market

National datasets capture sector-specific information on automation, digitalization, and other technological advances. This enables detailed analysis of their impact on job displacement, skill development, and shifts in productivity at the national level. Below we provide several measures which were adopted within the GI-NI project, such as technology adoption, automation, market concentration and firm's markup, automation exposure, and flexible wage components. We also give examples of how these measures were estimated with specific datasets. Moreover, where applicable, we provide cases of how the national datasets were linked with the EU-level datasets.

Technology adoption

The *German* data from the *IAB-ZEW Labour Market 4.0 Establishment Survey*² is designed to specifically address the role and importance of digital technologies in German establishments. It provides insights into the degree of digitalisation and automation of work equipment, as well as

¹ See the Annex for a detailed overview of the national data sources referred to in this section.

² See Table A in the annex with full description of each national data source.

other critical issues such as labour demand, training and education (Hanebrink et al., 2021). Interviewees were specifically asked to estimate the share of their work equipment in three technology levels: (i) frontier technologies associated with the Fourth Industrial Revolution, (ii) digital technologies associated with the Third Industrial Revolution, and (iii) manual technologies associated with the First and Second Industrial Revolutions. These estimates were used by Arntz et al. (2024) in the D3.1 GI-NI report to calculate the share of each technology level within establishments, distinguishing between technological advances in production and those in electronic office and communication systems.

The authors were able to link this survey with employment biographies from social security records: the data from the *IAB-ZEW-Labour Market 4.0-Establishment Survey* are linked to the IAB Employment History (BeH). This is a comprehensive dataset obtained from employers' social security declarations and containing information on employees' employment status, occupation, industry and earnings. This linkage made it possible to derive several firm-level indicators, such as occupational structure, total employment and average wage. These are used by Arntz et al. (2024) in the D3.1 GI-NI report to characterise the relationship between firms' technology adoption and employment structure.

Automation, market concentration and firm's markup

The automation measure used by Smolka and Taleb (2024) in the D3.1 GI-NI report is based on the *ESEE* survey. Launched in 1990, the *ESEE* annually collects comprehensive data from around 1,800 Spanish manufacturing firms, providing detailed insights into production processes, costs, prices, technological activities and employment.

An outstanding feature of the survey is the inclusion of firm-level information on the use of robots in production processes, which serves as a direct indicator of the level of automation. These data allow a robust analysis of how automation affects firms' productivity, employment dynamics and market behaviour. In addition, the *ESEE* provides data to calculate market concentration and firm-specific mark-ups:

- **Market concentration:** This is derived from firms' reports on the competitive environment of their primary market. Firms classify their markets according to the number of competitors: 10 or less competitors, 11-25 competitors, more than 25 competitors, or competitive (the market is "atomized");

- Firm-specific markups: These are calculated as a function of each firm's output price and marginal cost. The inputs for this calculation, such as costs and prices, are also taken from the ESEE survey, allowing a detailed assessment of pricing power and competitive dynamics.

Automation exposure

Using data from the PES in *Flanders*, in the D3.2 GI-NI report, Dabed et al. (2023) construct several job-related measures within the universe of job seekers. The PES data come from an online platform “*Mijn Loopbaan*” (“My Career”), where registration is mandatory for individuals claiming unemployment benefits. This requirement minimises voluntary selection bias, a common problem that often undermines the quality of platform-based datasets. Jobseekers' profiles on the platform include a list of occupations of interest linked to a matrix of task descriptions for the activities performed in these occupations. These job descriptions are part of the occupational classification system used for jobseeker profiles, allowing a comprehensive mapping of job preferences and task requirements.

The measure of interest is job-seeker's automation exposure defined as the likelihood that workers experience declining relative demand for their task competencies due to increased automation. In other words, this measure builds on the assumption that jobs that are intensive in routine tasks can be automated and displaced by machines. Routine activities are distinct from non-routine tasks that are challenging to automate since they require creativity, intuition, problem-solving, adaptability, and responsiveness to unscripted in-person interactions. For exposure to automation, an off-the-shelf measure is employed: occupational routine intensity based on O*NET (Acemoglu and Autor, 2011). This routine task intensity of occupations is cross-walked from SOC to ISCO and then merged at the four-digit ISCO-08 level. Intuitively, this measure describes to what extent work activities can be fully described by a set of rules and procedures (i.e., encoded in software) and carried out by machines (i.e., computers, industrial robots). To calculate the routine task intensity at the individual level, every job in the job seeker profile is averaged across the routine task intensity index.

Flexible wage components

Boza and Reizer (2023) apply the measure of flexible wage components (as overtime payments or performance payments) in the D3.3 GI-NI report to test if flexible wages have any

impact on productivity. This analysis is performed by gender to observe to which extent flexibility of earnings impacts gender pay gap. For this, the *HSES* and *ADMIN3* are utilised. The two surveys are matched together at the firm-year-occupation level to complement *ADMIN3* data with more detailed information on earnings (specifically, wage components earned by the workers in a specific month of the year). Additionally, *CIS* is used to study the relationship between the prevalence of flexible wage structure and innovation.

2.2. Globalisation and labour market

By using national-level data, it becomes possible to explore how globalisation affects labour demand, foreign direct investment, and trade. National datasets can track the changes in employment patterns and wage levels caused by global competition and international markets. For example, the measures which are related to the impact of globalisation on the labour market and addressed under the GI-NI project, are trade shock and offshoring.

Trade shock

The trade shock measure is developed in the D4.2 GI-NI report through two different angles: Konietzny and Los (2023) determine import exposure and trade exposure in *Germany*, while Peijen et al. (2023) focus on import exposure in *the Netherlands*. In both papers, the *WIOD data* is used to be linked with the national datasets.

Using the *SOEP survey*, Konietzny and Los (2023) estimate import exposure in Germany based on the trade-in-value-added and the input-output bodies of literature. By enriching this indicator with regional employment data, region-specific import exposure is evaluated for workers in each of the four business functions (management, marketing, R&D, and fabrication) and not based on the industry in which a worker is employed. At the later stage, trade exposure helps determine how exposure to imports in these four specific functions affects workers' likelihood of moving to other regions or switching functions. The *SOEP survey* provides a rare longitudinal dataset, enabling analysis of labour market dynamics, such as job satisfaction trends and occupational changes, which are in most cases unavailable in cross-sectional studies. This survey also includes the variables of job satisfaction level, giving insights about the quality of employment and worker well-being. Specific variables that are used for this analysis, are 'wage', 'years of education', 'marital status', 'number of persons in household', 'number of children', and 'household asset income'. Inputs derived from the *SOEP survey* are matched with *WIOD trade data*.

Peijen et al. (2023) illustrate the impact of exposure to import shocks on occupational changes, and through the lens of wages and job satisfaction of workers. The data from the Dutch *OSA Arbeidsaanbodpanel* at the worker level is combined with the WIOD trade data. The OSA *Arbeidsaanbodpanel* is rich in observing the impact of globalisation on specific occupations, distinguishing between short-term and long-term effects. This dataset also has a longitudinal aspect, which enables to track workers over time. From the OSA *Arbeidsaanbodpanel*, labour market outcomes focused on under this measure are ‘net monthly wage’, ‘annual wage income’ and ‘job satisfaction’. Adaptation to trade focuses on ‘changing occupation from business function to a different business function in a given year’ and ‘changing region of residence to a different region of residence in a given year’. Adaptation to changes in trade intensity focuses on ‘change of occupation’.

Offshoring

The impact of offshoring (meant as the relocation of certain parts of a fragmented production process abroad to low-wage countries) is studied in the D4.3 GI-NI report from the perspectives of the impact of domestic input price change, foreign acquisition of firms, and processing trade.

First, to study the effects of differences in domestic input prices on firm performance, employment and inequality in *Hungary*, Gaspar and Reizer (2024) calculate the index of firm-level domestic input price change in order to estimate the effects of the exposure to domestic costs and the exposure to foreign currency fluctuations on employment. For this, several datasets are used together. *Administrative BSD* that comes from tax declarations is linked to three surveys: *the MSUS*, *PRODCOM Survey*, and *ExIm of the HCSO*. Additionally, *ADMIN3* benefits the analysis by providing additional information on employees. All data are linked at the firm level.

Second, Petö and Reizer (2024) examine how foreign direct investment evolves over time, how firms’ tasks change after foreign acquisition, and how this impacts within-firm inequality in *Hungary*. Several datasets are employed. *ADMIN3 data* shows worker’s trajectory between firms and over time. *HCS* is the firm-level data with corporate income tax returns for the universe of the incorporated firms. To define ownership status of firms, data of the *CEU* is employed to be linked. Finally, *Education Statistics of the World Bank* provides the measure of the level of education in the source country.

Third, the concept of processing trade represents the production of one firm on behalf of another firm versus production on the firm's own account. Georgiev and Smolka (2024) employ this concept in *Bulgaria* in order to investigate firm heterogeneity depending on processing trade and with relation to the change and the composition of employment trends. *Processing Firms dataset* is the Bulgarian firm-product-level data on trade and production in the manufacturing sector. The production statistics dataset is merged with the trade statistics from customs records (on export-import operations), as well as with the business statistics from balance sheet data, income data, information on employment, assets, and subsidies (on the wage bill, total sales, materials expenditure, the number of employees, the capital stock etc.).

2.3. Migration and labour market

National datasets often include rich demographic and employment data on migrant populations, providing valuable insights into how migration influences labour supply, wage structures, and workforce diversity. Such data allow researchers to analyse both the challenges and opportunities that arise from migration and its effects on national economies. In the GI-NI report, the measures applied under the migration concept are cross-border immigration, labour assimilation, and consumer prices.

Cross-border immigration

The cross-border immigration measure was adopted by Lindner et al. (2023) in the D5.2 GI-NI report to study the impact of the opening of the Austrian border to *Hungarian workers* (following Hungary's accession to the EU in 2004) on employment and wages in the Hungarian border regions. Linking two datasets, *ADMIN3* and *AMS*, makes the analysis possible. *ADMIN3* provides data on employment status, occupation and monthly income, as well as anonymized firm identifiers, NUTS4 microregion of workers' home address and of the registered address of firms. Individual-level data on wages and employment is aggregated on the occupational level. Later, the average driving distance between the microregions in Hungary and the Austrian border is computed and only analysed for the microregions in Austria under 60-minute drive from the Hungarian border. Finally, *AMS* supplies the information on vacancies in Austria at the occupational level, in municipalities of workplace and starting date of the job for every vacancy.

Labour assimilation

In the D5.3 GI-NI report, Aldaz et al. (2024) study labour assimilation, which is perceived as the process of immigrants' integration into the labour market of the host country over time. Labour assimilation in Spain is analysed through the insertion, occupational integration and wage assimilation of immigrants. First, labour niche defines the concentration of certain demographic groups (such as migrants) in particular occupations, showing differences by origin. These niches can be measured using representation indices and are critical to understanding integration patterns in the labour market. Second, occupational segregation is estimated using indices that assess the uneven distribution of different demographic groups and shows the extent to which specific groups are excluded from certain occupations, contributing to broader labour market inequalities. Third, occupational mobility of unskilled native workers caused by the entry of immigrants into the labour market is analysed. Finally, occupational mobility of Spanish migrants is studied as a shift of their contribution group. The changes in the professional category are studied by comparing the first and last contract registered with the Social Security. The 10 Social Security contribution groups are used as general indicators of professional category levels: 1) Engineers, University Graduates, Management personnel; 2) Engineering Technicians, Experts and Qualified Assistants; 3) Administrative and Workshop Managers; 4) Unqualified Assistants; 5) Administrative Officials; 6) Subordinates; 7) Administrative Assistants; 8) First and second degree skilled workers; 9) Third degree skilled workers and specialists and 10) Unskilled workers.

The authors employ the *MCVL* which provides access to the complete employment history of the worker, their contribution bases since their entry into the labour market, allowing the study of the labour and wage assimilation of the immigrants, which is something lacking in other databases (cross-sectional). *MCVL* includes NUTS-2 and NUTS-3 regional data, alongside a gender variable, allowing for nuanced geographical and demographic analysis. Additionally, the *EU-LFS* is used to study labour niches, occupational segregation, as well as the impact of migration on occupational mobility of natives. Authors study both intra-EU labour mobility and immigration by defining the six groups of interest: male and female natives, male and female movers, and male and female immigrants.

Consumer prices

In the D5.3 GI-NI report, Smolka (2024) suggests that consumer prices may be influenced by the inequality between immigrants and natives. Migration data comes from the *Spanish Municipal*

Register (Padrón Municipal) of the INE at the province level. This register provides confidential information on the name, surname, sex, usual home address, nationality, passport number, place and date of birth of all Spanish residents. The significant advantage of this dataset consists in the fact that it is likely to include both documented and undocumented immigrants, because all immigrants were strongly incentivized to register at the time of arrival to obtain access to free medical care under the same conditions as Spanish nationals. The INE also provides data on consumer prices by 32 different product subgroups (such as food, non-alcoholic beverages, alcoholic beverages, tobacco, clothing, etc.). Matching the two datasets (on migration and on price consumer prices) at the province level allows constructing an equation of the impact of immigration on prices.

3. Challenges and Gaps in Existing European Data Sources

European-level datasets (such as *CIS*, *CVTS*, *ECS*, *EWCS*, *EU-LFS*, *EU-SILC*, *SES*, *Survey on the use of ICT in households and by individuals*, etc.) provide a very rich source of information on labour market dynamics, which is invaluable for making the right policy decisions. The *CIS* provides information on innovation in enterprises in the EU, EFTA and the candidate countries. The *CVTS* collects comparable data on continuing vocational training in enterprises. The *ECS* collects information on work organisation, workplace innovation, human resources practices, employee participation and social dialogue across Europe in the companies with at least 10 employees. The *EWCS* assesses working conditions of employees and the self-employed across Europe. The *EU-LFS* is a large household survey with quarterly results on labour participation of individuals above 15, both within and outside the labour force; it is conducted in all EU countries, four candidate countries, and three EFTA countries. The *EU-SILC* collects cross-sectional and longitudinal data on income, poverty, social exclusion, and living conditions. The *SES* gathers information on earnings at the enterprises with at least 10 employees in EU, candidate, and EFTA countries; *SES* is the only existing linked survey. The *Survey on the use of ICT in households and by individuals* provides yearly data on access to and use of ICT by households and individuals. The aggregated analysis based on this rich set of databases forms a central background for making recommendations on technological progress, tackling inequality, by taking into account migration trends in the context of globalisation. Below, we mention some important challenges and gaps in the EU-level data sources.

Greenan et al. (2023) point out that there is lack of harmonisation across datasets. For example, in the *CIS*, sector coverage is heterogeneous across countries, because some sectors are regarded as mandatory (like manufacturing, construction, trade, services), while other sectors may be voluntary. This leads to missing values for the sectorial variables, and thus impedes harmonised analysis. The *CVTS*, although provides rich information on continuing vocational training and skills at the employer level, is poorly aggregated at the sectoral level. On another note, while the *CVTS* covers enterprises with 10 to 1,000 employees, other datasets usually group employees' number by size categories, which limits researchers in the possibility to link datasets by this criterion.

In the *EU-LFS*, the *ISCO* variable is used across the EU but might have variations in implementation, for example, by the number of *ISCO* digits accounted: some countries report *ISCO* classification at different levels of precision. This is relevant for *NACE* classification too. Another

example from the EU-LFS, is the missing data for the “country of birth” for Germany before 2017, which could pose serious issues in studying migration trends.

Migration data in EU surveys tend to be aggregated, providing only a high-level view of migration flows. Information on migrants’ countries of origin is often grouped into broad regions, making it difficult to analyse labour market outcomes based on detailed country of origin data.

As a result, we know little about the patterns, skills and educational backgrounds of migrants, work experience, reasons for migration of individuals, specific nationalities or ethnic groups. At the same time, these factors are crucial for the preparation of labour market integration policies, as such analysis provides background for the types of jobs migrants obtain, their wage trajectories and their career progression. The EU-LFS, for example, includes an ad-hoc module on immigration, but this module is conducted not regularly (for example, this ad hoc module was conducted in 2008, 2014 and 2021), resulting in insufficient data across survey rounds. Additionally, the information collected varies significantly from one round to the next and is rarely longitudinal.

First of all, EU-level datasets struggle with utilising uniform definitions of migration-related variables. For example, terms such as “migrant”, “second-generation immigrant” and “refugee” are defined inconsistently across surveys, leading to different interpretations of data. Second, EU surveys have poor coverage of irregular migrants and temporary workers in official data sources. For example, the LFS, mainly covers migrants who are legally registered or formally employed. Third, due to the precarious nature of groups of migrants, their employment status may not be formal. This bias excludes a significant proportion of the migrant population working informally or irregularly, not to mention that their labour market experiences may be very different from those of formal workers. As a result, existing datasets do not reflect the full extent of migrants’ contribution to national or EU labour markets and the challenges they face. Finally, it is often difficult to link EU-level databases with each other. For example, although the EU-LFS and the ESS include variables on migration, they are often not integrated with other EU-level datasets, such as those on education, employment or health. This lack of linked frameworks prevents a holistic understanding of migrants’ experiences.

Access to up-to-date data may be limited. At the same time, data may not be collected in all regions, leading to data gaps, for example on marginalised or poorly documented populations. For example, micro-level data is available for CIS only for 15 countries. The CIS and the European ICT usage surveys provide rich insights at the enterprise level, but access is largely limited to aggregated data. This limitation prevents detailed analyses of how technology adoption varies across firms or

sectors and limits the ability to explore interdependencies between variables. Similarly, while individual-level data are available in surveys such as the EWCS, the lack of comparable micro-data integration between the firm and the employee makes holistic analysis less efficient (Greenan et al., 2023).

Sectoral and geographical coverage also remains inconsistent across datasets. For example, the CIS has different sectoral coverage across countries, with some sectors being primary and others optional, leading to different data availability. This problem may be deteriorated by missing values in the datasets, which would make comparison across countries and sectors difficult. In addition, datasets such as the European ICT usage survey cover enterprises with ten or more employees, excluding small enterprises which are often crucial for understanding technological change in the sectors with small-scale businesses.

Current EU datasets face several gaps in the analysis of technological change on labour markets, given the complexity and digital transformation. Existing data often fail to capture key aspects such as the rate of technological adoption across sectors or its impact on labour demand and skill requirements. Missing data or lack of a longitudinal approach in collecting data can negatively impact analyses and policy-making. To our knowledge, only the EU-SILC takes into account a longitudinal approach in datasets, while other surveys do not adopt this strategy yet.

One of the main limitations of EU-level data is the lack of a linked employer-employee framework, which makes it difficult to analyse how employer practices affect employees' labour market outcomes. While individual datasets capture information at either the employer or employee level, they do not provide a linked perspective due to privacy restrictions, methodological differences and data standardisation. As a result, the impact of specific employer policies on workers' pay, working conditions, job quality, productivity and overall labour market dynamics remains unknown or poorly estimated.

Some of the existing surveys, such as the EWCS and the ECS, examine employer and employee perspectives separately, but there is no mechanism to carry out joint analysis. As a result, researchers use indirect methods such as data aggregation or statistical modelling to merge datasets and conduct relevant analysis. Furthermore, the lack of homogeneous identifiers across these surveys makes it difficult to establish links between employer and employee datasets.

The lack of a relevant approach to linking employer-employee frameworks is particularly relevant in the context of rapid technological change, which is reshaping the European labour market. Researchers need to address the concepts of the impact of digitalisation, automation and

organisational restructuring on the basis of quality data and by considering the interaction between firm-level practices and individual labour market outcomes. While national initiatives, based on the Meadow Guidelines (Greenan et al., 2010), made progress in linking surveys in countries such as Germany, Denmark and Finland, a comparable EU-wide framework is still missing.

Linked databases that capture both employer and employee dynamics are essential for several reasons. First, by combining the two approaches, researchers can analyse how firm-level practices affect workers. For example, how do wage-setting policies, investments in training or innovative technologies affect employment conditions, job satisfaction and productivity. Second, linked datasets also provide the basis for multi-level analysis to disentangle organisational and individual effects on labour market outcomes, or vice versa. Finally, a harmonised linked dataset at EU level would allow for more complex research, shedding light on how different reforms affect employer-employee dynamics across Member States. This, in turn, would provide the basis for designing targeted labour market policies that benefit both workers and firms.

Several strategies are needed to increase the number of linked surveys at the EU level. More efforts are needed to harmonise data collection in existing surveys, for example through common variables and standardised classifications. In addition, initiatives such as the SES should be extended to include larger samples: the SES uses linked employer-employee sample frames in France and Italy. Overall, the establishment of a centralised European business register containing information on all European enterprises could provide a good basis for data linkage and statistical matching.

4. Framework for EU Data Enrichment and Concluding Remarks

The challenges and opportunities in enriching EU-level data to address labour market dynamics through technological change, globalisation, and migration highlight an urgent need for a more integrated and harmonised data framework in EU-level and national datasets. Existing datasets provide valuable insights into specific aspects of labour market. At the same time significant gaps remain, particularly in linking employer and employee perspectives, improving data harmonisation, the quality of migration data, as well as enlarging dataset sample sizes and incorporating longitudinal elements. The holistic framework for EU data enrichment should focus on the following key elements.

Linkage of employer and employee data

The lack of linked employer-employee datasets at EU level limits the ability to examine how organisational practices affect individual labour market outcomes. Establishing such links through harmonised surveys or innovative methods such as data linkage and statistical matching is essential. An example is the platform “Mijn Loopbaan” (“*My Career*”) where the PES in *Flanders* collects detailed employment data and matches it with employer information; detailed task-competency profiles are constructed from job seekers’ preferences and competencies. These are linked with administrative data. Another example is *ADMIN3*, which integrates employee data with administrative records from employers in order to track employment histories. The *IAB-ZEW-Labour Market 4.0-Establishment Survey* which data is linked to administrative social security records of all workers employed in the surveyed *German* enterprises. This data integration enables the study of how innovation influences employment and skills. In 2010, the harmonised framework for survey data linkage was proposed by the Meadow project (Greenan et al., 2010). Within this project, relevant guidelines were developed in order to facilitate the joint analysis of the datasets collected from both employers and employees, applicable to both public and private sectors. For example, one key recommendation from these guidelines is to design questionnaires for the collection of harmonised data across different countries. Meadow-inspired surveys at the national level offer the potential to answer critical policy questions on wage dynamics, job quality, and productivity.

While the *ex-ante* coordination of surveys is likely to be difficult to implement EU wide, an *ex-post* linkage between existing EU-level datasets may be adopted. This can be performed using different strategies: record linkage, statistical matching, data aggregation and multilevel modelling.

Harmonisation across datasets

Current EU datasets, such as the *EWCS* and the *EU-LFS*, often lack compatibility due to different definitions, classifications and survey methodologies. Harmonising these elements would allow better cross-survey analysis and more robust conclusions. Standardisation of occupational and sectoral classifications³ and the introduction of common identifiers are necessary solutions. Additional efforts are also necessary to harmonise the definitions, concepts, and measures.

The *SOEP* is linked to administrative data on enterprises through record linkage or, in other words, through deterministic matching and perfect correspondence between business identifiers and administrative records. The EU should develop more practices of this kind to increase the number of surveys available for exact record linkage. At the same time, thanks to having the same sampling units across different surveys, integrating surveys is enabled via statistical matching. However, as highlighted by Seghir (2021), employer and employee data at EU level are derived from different sampling units, making statistical matching infeasible. The only currently viable solution for data integration is to aggregate information to a common level between the datasets before merging them. Data aggregation is considered to be the most flexible approach to integrating datasets. However, it is important to recognise that the level of aggregation chosen affects not only the precision of the data, but also its accuracy and the degree of heterogeneity preserved between individuals. Balancing these trade-offs is critical to achieving meaningful and reliable integration results.

Improved migration data

Migration data in EU surveys tend to be aggregated, providing only a high-level view of migration flows. To address this, EU surveys should include more detailed information on migrants' educational backgrounds, professional experiences, and motivations for migrating. Longitudinal tracking of migration trajectories and better coverage of irregular migrants and temporary workers would also significantly enhance the understanding of labour market integration. Data from the *Padrón Municipal* is likely to include both documented and undocumented immigrants at the

³ Regarding the number of digits and correspondence between older and newer classifications.

province level in *Spain*, due to the incentive for all foreigners to register at the time of arrival to get access to free medical care.

Increasing sample sizes and incorporating longitudinal elements

Increasing sample sizes and incorporating longitudinal dimensions are important to include wider population categories that may be less represented, marginalized, or reach smaller or remote regions. Striving for larger sample sizes for linked employer-employee datasets could improve the reliability of data linkage and statistical matching. Longitudinal surveys are crucial for understanding labour market transitions, career progression, or training programs effectiveness. Adding a longitudinal dimension to surveys like the *EWCS* or the *ECS* would allow tracking changes over time and evaluate policies more effectively. Among national dataset examples, it is worth mentioning the *MCVL* which captures a representative sample of the Spanish workforce and pensioners, allowing for longitudinal insights into career trajectories. The *SOEP* tracks individuals and households annually, providing important longitudinal insights into socio-economic variables like wages and job satisfaction. *ADMIN3* offers monthly employment records for over 14 years, enabling detailed analyses of wages and employment. Enlarging sector-specific data coverage could be learnt from the *ESEE*, which provides sector-specific data for Spanish manufacturing firms, with insights into strategies and performance over nearly three decades, or from the *PRODCOM* Survey, which captures manufacturing firm performance across Hungary and in the EU, stressing attention on the sectoral analysis productivity. The *OSA* observes individuals through a longitudinal dimension, which enables analysing labour market of both short- and long-term trends. Overall, the SES is requested by Eurostat and is carried out in every EU country following a repeated cross-sectional structure. However, unlike most other countries, the Hungarian version of the SES has a unique panel structure at the firm level and includes a unique firm identifier, which allows the data to be merged with administrative balance sheet data for a more comprehensive analysis.

Because of strict anonymisation rules of EU-level databases with the objective of data integration, possible narrowing of the scope of research may largely impact the quality of scientific results due to the small cell size. For this reason, it is important to increase sample size of EU-level surveys not to lose the validity of obtained results. As another solution, questionnaires may be shortened in order to improve the response rates of surveys.

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Annex

Table A. Detailed description of the national data used in the papers

IAB-ZEW-Labour Market 4.0-Establishment Survey	
Overview	Conducted by the IAB and ZEW, this survey collects novel data on the actual adoption of frontier technologies, specifically firms' use of frontier (latest, cutting-edge) and digital technologies, as well as manual technologies. It aims to understand technology integration within firms and how it influences workforce composition and tasks. Survey data is linked to administrative social security records of all workers employed at the surveyed firms.
Target population	All German establishments with at least one employee subject to social security contributions, as registered with the German Federal Employment Agency.
Target sample	A representative sample of 2,032 German manufacturing and service firms.
Sample design	The firms in the survey are a stratified random sample of all German firms with at least one employee subject to social security contributions which are registered at the German Federal Employment Agency. The German administrative data contains information on single-location firms and does not contain information on whether these firms belong to a multi-site company or not.
Sample size	A representative sample of 2,032 German manufacturing and service firms. The survey was carried out between March and May 2016, with a response rate of 31.5%.
Reference year	2016
Geographical coverage	Germany
Encuesta Sobre Estrategias Empresariales (ESEE)	
Overview	This annual survey, conducted during 1990-2018, is aimed at collecting information on the evolution, strategies, behaviours, and performance of manufacturing firms.
Target population	
Target sample	The sampling of the data in 1990 had a two-tier structure taking into account the size of firms measured by the number of employees. Specifically, survey questionnaires were sent out to all large firms that had more than 200 employees, and to a sample of small firms that had between 10 and 200 employees. Small firms were chosen based on stratified, proportional and systematic sampling with a random seed, where a firm's industry affiliation and size class were used as stratification variables. The survey distinguishes between 20 different industries, where each industry is given by a set of 3-digit NACE Rev. 2 products. The sampling of the data is done in such a way that the ESEE data are representative of the Spanish manufacturing sector at large

	when the sampling properties are taken into account. For this, sampling weights (as the inverse sampling probability of a firm relative to the population of firms by industry-size stratum in 2010) is used based on data from the Spanish Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE).
Sample design	firms active in the manufacturing sector
Sample size	Roughly 1,900 firms active in the manufacturing sector
Reference year	1990-2018
Geographical coverage	Spain
Public Employment Services (PES) in Flanders	
Overview	<p>The PES in Flanders is organized at the regional level and utilises an online platform called "Mijn Loopbaan" ("My Career"). This platform is mandatory for all job seekers claiming unemployment benefits. It supports job seekers by allowing them to list job preferences and competencies.</p> <p>The piece of information that is obtained from this profile is the list of occupations that job seekers are interested to work in and their experience. This list may contain more than one job, on average job seekers list 4 different jobs. These jobs are classified according to a very detailed classification: 643 occupations with each up to three levels of experience. Each of these jobs are linked to one or more detailed task descriptions. This task matrix was built on the classification by the French PES (ROME-v3) combined with information from expert surveys in Belgium. The descriptions of jobs and the experiences of job seekers are used to construct a task-competency profile for each individual in sample.</p> <p>Administrative data from the PES contains both information from the profiles of job seekers (directly related to their job search) and this is matched to more general administrative data that provides with background information.</p>
Target population	Newly registered unemployed job seekers receiving benefits. This excludes individuals who were unemployed in the last six months and those who lost jobs involuntarily. Labour market entrants looking for work are also included, but job seekers older than 55 are not required to search actively and hence are excluded.
Target sample	All individuals who registered as unemployed and created profiles on the "Mijn Loopbaan" platform between March 1 and September 9, 2021.
Sample design	All registered unemployed individuals within the specified timeframe who meet the criteria for unemployment benefits. The platform's mandatory nature helps avoid biases such as voluntary selection.
Sample size	33,352 individuals who entered unemployment during the study period.
Reference year	2021, between March 1 - September 9
Geographical coverage	Belgium

European Company Survey (ECS)	
Overview	Eurofound and Cedefop joined forces to carry out the fourth European Company Survey (ECS) in 2019. The ECS 2019 collects data in over 20,000 establishments on workplace practices with regard to work organisation, human resource management, skills use, skills strategies, digitalisation, direct employee participation and social dialogue. It allows for the identification of those bundles of workplace practices that work particularly well in creating win–win outcomes: situations where workers are facilitated and motivated to use their skills to the full, share their knowledge and insights with colleagues and management, and identify opportunities to improve both themselves and the work process as a whole, allowing establishments to thrive.
Target population	Senior managers in charge of personnel and, where present, official employee representatives in establishments with 10 or more employees in all sectors involved in ‘market activities’
Target sample	The sample size targets of MM interviews differ by country, they range from 250 in small countries to 1,500 in larger countries.
Sample design	Procedures differed between countries, using the best quality sampling frame that was available. Sampling was always stratified by establishment/company size and broad sector of activity (manufacturing, construction and services). In countries with an establishment-level sampling frame, stratified random probability sampling was applied. In countries with a company-level sampling frame, stratified random probability sampling was applied and subsequently a screening procedure was used to randomly select up to three establishments in multi-establishment companies.
Sample size	A total of 21,869 management interviews were completed, ranging from 122 in Cyprus to 1,498 in Italy. A total of 3,073 employee representative interviews were carried out, ranging from 3 in Cyprus to 467 in Finland. Finally, for 1,835 establishments both a management interview and an employee representative interview were completed, ranging from 2 in Ireland to 284 in France.
Reference year	Data are available for reference years 2004, 2009, 2013, 2019
Geographical coverage	27 EU Member States and the United Kingdom
ADMIN3 (Hungarian Administrative Linked Employer-Employee Dataset)	
Overview	Prepared by the Centre for Economic and Regional Studies (KRTK), this dataset provides comprehensive data on employment history for a random sample of 50% of the Hungarian population from 2003 to 2017, focusing on private sector employment. Data provides information on employment status, occupation and income at a monthly frequency. The database contains anonymized firm identifiers as well as the balance sheet and income statement of the employing firms. This data is used to estimate the effect of price changes on wage inequality and worker composition (for a detailed data description see Sebok (2019)). The database comprises wage and occupation (four-digit ISCO code)

	information on a random 50 percent sample of the Hungarian population and balance sheet data for the employer. We use the database to compute the average wage and within-firm wage inequality measures. In contrast to the other databases used in the study, this database does not share the same anonymized firm identifier. That is why we follow the strategy of Card et al. [2016] and use balance sheet information and statistical matching to connect the wage information of Admin3 and MSUS. The matching procedure is explained in detail by Boza and Reizer.
Target population	Hungarian employees in both private and public sectors.
Target sample	Random sample of approximately 5.4 million individuals, with about 3.4 million observed as employees.
Sample design	Stratified sample representing a significant portion of the Hungarian workforce.
Sample size	Includes 5.4 million individuals, with monthly records from January, April, June, and October.
Reference year	2003-2017
Geographical coverage	Hungary
Hungarian Structure of Earning Survey (HSES)	
Overview	This annual survey contains detailed data on wage components (the base wage, bonuses, premia, and overtime payments) earned in May, collected annually for Hungarian firms. The survey contains the balance sheet of firms. At the firm level, the HSES has a panel structure. The Hungarian SES has a unique firm identifier that allows to merge the data to administrative balance sheet data.
Target population	Hungarian private and public sector workers, focusing on wage structure.
Target sample	A sample of workers, covering firms with more than 50 employees annually and a random selection for firms between 5 and 50 employees.
Sample design	Stratified sampling by firm size, providing detailed earnings and wage component data. Firms with less than 50 have to report wages for all workers while larger firms have to report wages for a 10 percent sample of workers. Workers are in the sample if they were born on the 5th, 15th, or 25th day of the month.
Sample size	Around 10,000 firms and 170,000 workers annually.
Reference year	Since 2003 annually
Geographical coverage	Hungary
German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP)	
Overview	The SOEP is one of the largest and longest-running multidisciplinary household surveys worldwide. Every year, approximately 30,000 people in 22,000 households are interviewed for the SOEP study. The SOEP is also a research-driven infrastructure based at DIW Berlin. As part of the Leibniz Association, the SOEP receives funding from the

	Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) and from Germany's state (Länder) governments. This survey captures socio-economic variables of German individuals and households. It provides individual-level data on labour earnings, job satisfaction, occupation, and geographic location.
Target population	Germany's resident population
Target sample	Unknown, the documentation (Göbel et al., 2019) only reports on the sampling procedures (including oversampling of specific types of households) and on the sample size.
Sample design	SOEP only uses random probability samples. General population samples typically draw on a nation-wide two-stage stratified sampling procedure. First, nation-wide sample points are sampled by federal state and municipality size. To secure efficient face-to-face interviewing, the number of regional sample points ranges between 125 and 985 per sample. A second stratification stage distinguishes natives and migrants. SOEP relied on two types of sampling frames: (a) screening in large telephone surveys of the fieldwork organization KANTAR Public; and (b) register data (see Göbel et al., 2019, for more detail).
Sample size	15,000 households/30,000 individuals
Reference year	2000-2011 (1984-2021 available, but not used due to limited coverage of other data needed for the analysis)
Geographical coverage	Germany
Dutch Labour Supply Panel (OSA Arbeidsaanbodpanel)	
Overview	The labour supply panel has been set up to map various aspects of labour supply (employed, job seekers and non-participating) over time, in The Netherlands. Important themes are labour mobility and job search behavior. Other topics include working hours, opinions about work, the current job and colleagues. The surveys were conducted by OSA until 2010, afterwards the Netherlands Institute for Social Research (SCP) has become responsible for this task.
Target population	The Dutch population aged 16-66 years old (the working age population), from 2004 onwards also including students.
Target sample	For the 2020 wave about 8,100 individuals were approached to participate.
Sample design	Participants in the previous wave are asked to respond again. 20-30% of the potential respondents do not participate again (they might have grown too old, or refuse), and are replaced by new respondents. This also ensures that younger generations remain sufficiently represented. The new respondents are drawn by Statistics Netherlands from the "Basisregistratie Personen". To maximize the representativeness of the sample, 39 strata are discerned. For details, see Josten & de Voogd-Hamelink (2022).

Sample size	About 4,800 individuals per wave.
Reference year	1985, and from 1986 a wave once every two years. For the analysis, only the 2002-2008 waves were used, partly because of changes in the structure of the survey and partly because the number of individuals of interest (given the research question who had participated in 2004 still present in the 2010 wave was considered too small.
Geographical coverage	The Netherlands.
Balance Sheet Database (BSD)	
Overview	BSD contains data on firm-level balance sheets and income statements from tax declarations. Administrative tax declaration forms are provided by the National Tax and Customs Administration. It is possible to compute the change of revenue and employment and total factor productivity between 2005 and 2020 without sample attrition.
Target population	All firms practicing double-entry bookkeeping.
Target sample	Firms with active reporting across 2005-2020.
Sample design	N/A
Sample size	N/A
Reference year	2005-2020
Geographical coverage	Hungary
Material and Service Use Survey (MSUS)	
Overview	Firm-level data on the material and service expenditure of a sample of firms every five years. Firm-level inputs are categorized into 120 distinct categories and firms report total material expenditure in each category, but no quantities and unit prices are provided. To overcome this problem, domestic price indices are derived from the PRODCOM database. The two data sets are linked through CPA codes of the input groups (Statistical Classification of Products by Activity).
Target population	Firms with material expenses exceeding HUF 500 million (EUR 2.03 million at the 2005 average exchange rate).
Target sample	Firms meeting the expense threshold.
Sample design	Mandatory reporting every five years.
Sample size	N/A
Reference year	2005, 2010, 2015.
Geographical coverage	Hungary
PRODCOM Survey (short for Production Communautaire)	
Overview	Firm-level data on domestic sales and exports at the product level.
Target population	Manufacturing firms with 20+ employees; firms not in manufacturing participate if they made at least HUF 500 million in sales. Smaller manufacturing firms are represented by a random sample.
Target sample	Larger manufacturing firms plus a random sample of smaller firms.

Sample design	Census with sampling for smaller entities.
Sample size	N/A
Reference year	Annual
Geographical coverage	Hungary and all EU countries
Export-Import Database (ExIm) of the HCSO	
Overview	Tracks export and import statistics at the firm-product level, including prices and quantities. This data includes firm product level export and import statistics (prices and quantities as well). For trade outside the European Union, the database covers the universe of firms and their exported and imported products. For international trade within the European Union, firms have to report their export and import quantities as well as their prices by product and country if their total exports and imports are above a specific threshold.
Target population	Hungarian firms involved in international trade, especially those above reporting thresholds. The threshold was HUF 100 million (EUR 402,000) for exports and HUF 40 million (EUR 161,300) for imports in 2005. The HCSO monitors on the basis of administrative value-added tax records whether firms exceed the thresholds. As a consequence, the coverage of the database is close to complete, and it accounts for 93-97 percent of total export and import value.
Target sample	Firms meeting reporting thresholds for EU and non-EU trade.
Sample design	Coverage is approximately 93-97% of total trade value.
Sample size	Extensive due to comprehensive trade data.
Reference year	Annual reporting.
Geographical coverage	Hungary and EU-wide trade.
Hungarian Customs Statistics (HCS)	
Overview	<p>Hungarian Customs Statistics are collected by the Hungarian Central Statistical Office (KSH) and the National Tax and Customs Administration of Hungary (NAV). These statistics are part of the international trade data system and provide essential insights into imports and exports between Hungary and other countries. They help monitor economic trends, trade flows, and the impact of tariffs and trade policies on the national economy.</p> <p>The dataset records exports and imports of trading firms in a 6-digit Harmonised System (HS) product breakdown. The database consists of the amount and unit value of import and export by country, year, and products. The data is matched to the Balance Sheet record of the firm based on a unique firm identifier. It is not possible to merge it with the administrative employment and wage data due to administrative restrictions.</p>
Target population	All entities and businesses engaged in the import and export of goods. This includes Hungarian enterprises, international companies operating in Hungary, and occasionally individuals who import/export goods for

	personal use if these transactions meet the reporting threshold.
Target sample	Customs data is gathered for every import and export transaction above a certain value threshold as stipulated by EU and national regulations, meaning each transaction that requires customs documentation is recorded and contributes to the data.
Sample design	All relevant transactions.
Sample size	All recorded customs declarations.
Reference year	2004 – 2016
Geographical coverage	Hungary
Processing Firms	
Overview	The dataset covers Bulgarian firms engaged in processing trade – production on behalf of another firm rather than for their own account. These firms perform specific tasks for foreign or domestic headquarters, reflecting Bulgaria’s role as an offshore destination in Europe.
Target population	The dataset includes all manufacturing firms with annual revenue over 60,000 EUR and covers a broad spectrum of industries. It captures firms that specialize in various levels of processing, focusing on labour-intensive production roles within the manufacturing sector.
Target sample	The data includes both pure processing firms and those that engage in processing alongside own-manufacturing.
Sample design	The sample design allows analysis of transitions between processing and own-manufacturing, providing detailed insights into firm behaviour over time.
Sample size	The dataset includes roughly 7,000 firms per year, with a total of 13,838 unique firms.
Reference year	2008 – 2015
Geographical coverage	Bulgaria
Vacancy Register of the Austrian Public Employment Service (Arbeitsmarktservice, AMS)	
Overview	The dataset tracks job vacancies across Austria, compiled by the Austrian Public Employment Service. It includes information on job openings, their characteristics, duration, and unemployment benefits payments. It is used to study labour demand dynamics, including the effects of cross-border employment. The dataset contains 60 percent of the total number of vacancy postings in Austria.
Target population	All job vacancies advertised through Austria.
Target sample	N/A
Sample design	The dataset captures all job vacancies listed with the Austrian Public Employment Service.
Sample size	The exact sample size is variable, as it depends on the number of job listings recorded.
Reference year	N/A

Geographical coverage	Austria
Muestra Continua de Vidas Laborales (MCVL) - Continuous Working Life Survey	
Overview	The Spanish Continuous Working Life Survey (MCVL) is a set of anonymised microdata of the Spanish Social Security System. The information from the Social Security is completed with data from the Continuous Municipal Register (National Statistics Institute-INE) and with data from the State Tax Administration Agency. It constitutes a representative sample of all persons related to Social Security during the reference year. It contains information about each individual considering, among other aspects, its personal characteristics, its working activity and information about the firm. The MCVL allows the reconstruction of the labour history of these individuals.
Target population	The target population is essentially made up of people who are registered in the Social Security system, both affiliated workers and pensioners (who receive a contributory pension).
Target sample	4% of the total individuals related to the Spanish Social Security in the reference year (more than one million individuals).
Sample design	A simple random sampling is applied, and a panel structure is maintained since the first random extraction in 2004. The units are extracted maintaining the codes of the first extraction, insofar as they continue to be related to Social Security, and they are renewed in a representative manner with new incorporations.
Sample size	The population and sample size varies in each reference year. Thus, for example, the reference population was 31,743,051 people in 2019. The sample size is set at 3.9973% of this population, a total of 1,268,856 individuals.
Reference year	It is conducted since 2004 yearly. The last available edition is 2021. Reference year for the study is 2019.
Geographical coverage	Spain
Spanish Municipal Register (Padrón Municipal)	
Overview	This data records all residents in Spain, including both documented and undocumented immigrants. Registration in this system is mandatory for all residents, which ensures comprehensive coverage. This register includes data such as name, surname, sex, domicile, nationality, passport number, and place and date of birth. All immigrants were strongly incentivized to register at the time of arrival, as the Law on the Rights and Freedoms of Aliens in Spain and their Social Integration in the year 2000 (<i>Ley Organica 4/2000, artículo 12</i>) entitled all foreigners (with or without legal residence permits) to free medical care under the same conditions as Spanish nationals provided they were registered in the Municipal Register.
Target population	The target population includes all residents in Spain, irrespective of their immigration status.

Target sample	N/A
Sample design	The entire population of residents is included in the register.
Sample size	The entire population of residents is included in the register.
Reference year	1997-2013
Geographical coverage	All provinces of Spain, although the analysis excludes the enclaves Ceuta and Melilla due to their special geographical location in North Africa.

GI-NI PROJECT IDENTITY

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Growing Inequality:^[1]_{SEP} a novel integration of transformations research — GI-NI

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Consortium

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